

Morphometric Study of Coracoid Process in Adult Dry Human Scapula and its Clinical Implications in Telangana Region

M. Padmavathi¹, Zainab Fatima², Niveditha Samala³, D. Sudhakara Babu⁴

¹Professor, Department of Anatomy, Osmania Medical College, Hyderabad.

²Senior Resident, Department of Anatomy, Government Medical College, Sangareddy.

³Assistant Professor, Department of Anatomy, Osmania Medical College, Hyderabad.

⁴Professor & Hod, Government Medical College, Nizamabad.

Received: 15-04-2022 / Revised: 18-05-2022 / Accepted: 01-06-2022

Corresponding author: Dr D. Sudhakara Babu

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Introduction: Coracoid process is a part of scapula it plays an important role in shoulder function. It arises from the antero-lateral aspect of the scapula. The coracoid process is joined to clavicle by the coracoclavicular ligament. The coracoid process gives attachment to coracoacromial ligament, coracohumeral ligament, coracoclavicular ligament and provides attachment to coracobrachialis and the short head of biceps brachii muscles.

Aim: To study the morphometric details of coracoid process of dried adult human scapula bones.

Objectives: To study the dimensions of coracoid process of dried adult human scapula like length, breadth, thickness, base height and base width of coracoid process and coraco-glenoid distance, and the types of coraco-glenoid space.

Design: Observational study.

Materials and Methods: The study was done on 100 dried adult human scapula bones (50 right and 50 left) of unknown sex available in the Department of Anatomy, Osmania Medical College, Koti, Hyderabad, and other medical colleges in Telangana. Damaged bones were omitted from the study. Coracoid process was studied for the following dimensions length, breadth, thickness, base height and base width of coracoid process and coraco-glenoid distance by using digital vernier calipers and the types of coraco-glenoid space were observed. These parameters were compared on both the sides, the results were tabulated and subjected to statistical analysis.

Results: The most predominant type of coraco-glenoid space was found to be the Type I - round bracket (63%) then Type II Square bracket (25%) and type III Fish hook (12%). All the parameters such as length, breath, thickness, base height, base width of coracoid process and coraco-glenoid distance have higher values on Right side when compared to left side but the difference was statistically insignificant (p value >0.05 is insignificant).

Conclusion: The study of variation of dimensions of coracoid process provides valuable information regarding the role of these parameters in etiology of subcoracoid impingement syndrome. It will also help the radiologist and orthopedic surgeons for diagnosing various pathologies and plan for surgical procedure on coracoid process. Also useful in biomechanical engineering for designing implants for total shoulder replacement.

Keywords: Coracoid Process, Base Height And Base Width Of Coracoid Process, Coraco-Glenoid Distance, Coraco-Glenoid Space.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided Original work is properly credited.

Introduction

The coracoid process is an osseous structure that projects forward and curves laterally, and arises from the superior border of the head of the scapula [1]. The coracoid process is joined to clavicle by the coracoclavicular ligament [2]. The lateral border of coracoid process gives attachment to coracoacromial ligament and inferiorly to coracohumeral ligament. The tip of coracoid provides attachment to coracobrachialis and the short head of biceps brachii muscles. On the dorsal surface of coracoid process there is attachment of coracoclavicular ligament. Surgeons often refer the coracoid process as the "lighthouse of the shoulder" because of its proximity to major neurovascular structures such as the brachial plexus and the axillary artery and vein, its role in guiding surgical approaches, and its utility as a landmark for other important structures in the shoulder [3].

Aim: To study the morphometric details of coracoid process of dried adult human scapula bones.

Design: Observational study.

Materials and Methods

The study was done on 100 dried adult human scapula bones (50 right and 50 left) of unknown sex available in the Department of Anatomy, Osmania Medical College, Koti, Hyderabad, and other medical colleges in Telangana. Damaged bones were omitted from the study. Coracoid process was studied for the following dimensions length, breadth, thickness, base height and base width of coracoid process and coraco-glenoid distance by using digital vernier calipers and the types of coraco-glenoid space were observed. These parameters were compared on both the sides,

the results were tabulated and subjected to statistical analysis.

Inclusion criteria: All dried adult Scapula bones (Non pathological bones) of both sides irrespective of sex and race.

Exclusion criteria: Damaged bones were omitted from the study.

Statistical Analysis

Mean, Standard deviation and P value are calculated using Microsoft Excel for Microsoft 365 (Version 2111).

The parameters taken were as follows: as seen in Fig-1 and Fig-2

1. Length of coracoid process: Measured from the tip of the coracoid process to the anterior end of the scapular notch at the superior scapular border with the help of vernier calliper.
2. Width of coracoid process: is the Antero-posterior distance at the midpoint on superior surface of coracoid process with the help of vernier calliper.
3. Thickness of coracoid process: is the supero-inferior distance 1cm posterior to the tip of coracoid Process with help of Vernier calliper.
4. Base height: is the maximum supero-inferior distance of the base i.e: Distance between supraglenoid tubercle to top of ascending portion of coracoid process [4]. measured with the help of Vernier calliper.
5. Base width: is the maximum lateral-medial distance of the base measured with the help of Vernier calliper.
6. Coraco-glenoid distance: distance measured from the anterior rim of the glenoid fossa, near supraglenoid tubercle

- to the tip of the coracoid process measured with the help of Vernier calliper.
7. Coraco-glenoid space was classified by Gallino *et al* [5] into
- Round bracket (Type I)
 - Square bracket (II)
 - Fish hook (III)

Figure 1: Points of measurement of – Length of coracoid process, width of coracoid process, Thickness of coracoid process and Coraco-glenoid distance. T- Thickness, cgd - Coraco-glenoid distance.

Figure 2: Points of measurements of – Base Height and Base Width of Coracoid Process.

Results

The present study was conducted on 100 dried adult human scapula bones (50 right and 50 left) . The most predominant type of coraco-glenoid space was found to be the Type I - round bracket (63%) then Type II Square bracket (25%) and then type III Fish hook (12%). In the present study the Mean Length

(in mm) of Coracoid Process was 40.0 ± 11.89 and 39.24 ± 2.29 on right and left side respectively. The Mean Breadth (in mm) of Coracoid Process was 14.08 ± 2.24 and 13.61 ± 1.98 on right and left side respectively. The Mean Thickness (in mm) of Coracoid

Process was 8.23 ± 2.85 and 7.99 ± 1.21 on right and left side respectively.

The Mean Base Height (in mm) of Coracoid Process was 22.16 ± 2.46 and 21.89 ± 3.42 on right and left side respectively. The Mean Base Width (in mm) of Coracoid Process was 10.59 ± 3.11 and 10.05 ± 2.54 on right and left side respectively. The Mean Coraco-glenoid

distance (in mm) was 27.3 ± 1.5 and 26.1 ± 3.3 on right and left side respectively.

All the parameters such as length, breadth, thickness, base height, base width of coracoid process and coraco-glenoid distance have higher values on Right side when compared to left side but the difference was statistically insignificant (p value >0.05 is insignificant) as seen in Table-1 & 2

Table 1: Types Of Coraco-Glenoid Space

Shape	Total (%)
Type- I (Round)	63(63%)
Type -II (Square)	25(25%)
Type -III (Fish Hook)	12(12%)

Figure 3: Coraco glenoid space.

Table 2: Obsevation Of Different Parameters Of Coracoid Process

Parameter	Mean± S.D(mm)		Average Mean± SD(mm)	P value
	Right	Left		
Length	40.0 ± 11.89	39.24 ± 2.29	39.62 ± 2.09	0.12
Breadth	14.08 ± 2.24	13.61 ± 1.98	13.85 ± 2.11	0.24
Thickness	8.23 ± 2.85	7.99 ± 1.21	8.11 ± 2.03	0.51
Base Height	22.16 ± 2.46	21.89 ± 3.42	22.03 ± 2.94	0.74
Base width	10.59 ± 3.11	10.05 ± 2.54	10.32 ± 2.85	0.56
Coraco-glenoid distance	27.3 ± 1.5	26.1 ± 3.3	26.7 ± 2.4	0.17

Discussion

Numerous procedures of open arthroscopic or surgical access to the shoulder refer to the coracoid Process hence it has been defined by Matsen *et al* as “the lighthouse of the shoulder” [6] and hence the study of variation of dimensions of coracoid process is significant.

In the present study, the mean and standard deviation of length of coracoid process on the right and left side was 40.0 ± 11.89 and 39.24 ± 2.29 . The difference between the mean Length of Coracoid process was more on right then left side but it was found to be statistically insignificant as p value was found to be 0.12 (p value >0.05 is insignificant).

The mean Length in the study done by Gumina *et al* [7] (1999) and Das SR *et al* [8] (2020), was almost similar when compared to the present study.

The mean Length in the study done by Piyawinijwong *et al* [9] (2004), Coskun *et al* [10] (2006) and Verma U *et al* [11] (2017) was lesser when compared to the present study.

The mean Length in the study done by Gallino *et al* [5] (1998), Rajan S *et al* [4] (2014), Pahuja N and Singh [12] (2014), Khan R *et al* [13] (2019), was higher when compared to the present study.

This shows results varies among regions.

The comparison of Mean Length of Coracoid Process among different population is seen in Table-3.

In the present study, the mean and standard deviation of breadth of coracoid process on the right and left side was 14.08 ± 2.24 and 13.61 ± 1.98 . The difference between the mean Breadth of Coracoid process was more on right then left side but it was found to be statistically insignificant as p value was found to be 0.51 (p value >0.05 is insignificant).

The mean Breadth of coracoid process in the study done by Rajan S *et al* [4] (2014), Das SR *et al* [8] (2020) was almost similar when compared to the present study.

The mean Breadth of coracoid process in the study done by Piyawinijwong *et al* [9] (2004) and Khan R *et al* [13] (2019), was lesser when compared to the present study.

The mean Breadth in the study done by Verma U *et al* [11] (2017) and Das SR *et al* [8] (2020) was higher when compared to the present study.

This shows results varies among regions.

The comparison of Mean Breadth of Coracoid process among different population is seen in Table-3.

In the present study, the mean and standard deviation of thickness of coracoid process on the right and left side was 8.23 ± 2.85 and 7.99 ± 1.21 . The difference between the mean Thickness of Coracoid process was more on right then left side but it was found to be statistically insignificant as p value was found to be 0.51 (p value >0.05 is insignificant).

The mean Thickness of coracoid process in the study done by Das SR *et al* [8] (2020) was almost similar when compared to the present study.

The mean Thickness of coracoid process in the study done by Piyawinijwong *et al* [9] (2004), Coskun *et al* [10] (2006), Rajan S *et al* [4] (2014), Pahuja N and Singh [12] (2014) and Verma U *et al* [11] (2017), was lesser when compared to the present study.

This shows results varies among regions.

The comparison of Mean Thickness of Coracoid process among different population is seen in Table-3.

In the present study, the mean and standard deviation of base height of coracoid process on the right and left side was 22.16 ± 2.46 and 21.89 ± 3.42 . The difference between the mean Base Height of Coracoid process was more on right then left side but it was found to be statistically insignificant as p value was found to be 0.74 (p value >0.05 is insignificant).

The mean Base Height of coracoid process in the study done by Das SR *et al* [8] (2020) was slightly Higher when compared to the present study.

This shows results varies among regions.

The comparison of Mean Base Height of Coracoid process among different population is seen in Table-3.

In the present study, the mean and standard deviation of base width of coracoid process on the right and left side was 10.59 ± 3.11 and 10.05 ± 2.54 . The difference between the mean Base Width of Coracoid process was more on right then left side but it was found to be statistically insignificant as p value was found to be 0.56 (p value >0.05 is insignificant).

The mean Base Width of coracoid process in the study done by Das SR *et al* [8] (2020) was slightly Higher when compared to the present study.

This shows results varies among regions.

The comparison of Mean Base Width of Coracoid process among different population is seen in Table-3.

In the present study, the mean and standard deviation of coraco-glenoid distance on the

right and left side was 27.3 ± 1.5 and 26.1 ± 3.3 . The difference between the mean Coraco-glenoid Distance was more on right then left side but it was found to be statistically insignificant as p value was found to be 0.17 (p value >0.05 is insignificant).

The mean Coraco-glenoid Distance in the study done by Das SR *et al* [8] (2020) was slightly Higher when compared to the present study.

This shows results varies among regions.

The comparison of Mean Base Width of Coracoid process among different population is seen in Table-3.

Type of coraco-glenoid Space: In the present study Type I(round bracket)was the most common type seen in 63% of the scapulae. The second most common type was Type II (square bracket) seen in 25 % which was found and least is Type III (fish hooked) in 12 % The findings of the current study was similar to the findings of the Gumina *et al*[7] (1999), Verma U *et al* [11] (2017) and Das SR *et al* [8] (2020).

The comparison of Types of coraco-glenoid Space among different population is seen in Table-4.

Table 3: Length, Breadth, Thickness, Base Height, Base Width and Coraco-glenoid distance.

Authors	Population	Length (mm)	Breadth (mm)	Thickness (mm)	Base Height	Base Width	Coraco-glenoid distance
Gallino <i>et al</i> [5] (1998)	Egyptian	41.10	-	-	-	-	-
Gumina <i>et al</i> [7] (1999)	Italian	38.15			-	-	-
Piyawinijwong <i>et al</i> [9] (2004)	Thai	37.50	13.50	6.6	-	-	-
Coskun <i>et al</i> [10](2006)	Turkish	19.40	-	7.83	-	-	-
Rajan S <i>et al</i> [4] (2014)	North Indian	40.43	13.77	7.03	-	-	-
Pahuja N and Singh[12] (2014)	Indian	41.00	-	7.40	-	-	-

Verma U <i>et al</i> [11] (2017)	North Indian	35.54	14.50	7.95	-	-	-
Khan R <i>et al</i> [13] (2019)	South African	41.0	13.7	-	-	-	27.8
Das SR <i>et al</i> [8] (2020)	Odisha	39.91	14.00	8.32	22.87	10.50	
Present study	Telangana	39.62	13.85	8.11	22.03	10.32	26.7

Table 4: Coracoglenoid space (CGS)

Authors	TYPE-I CGS	TYPE-II CGS	TYPE-III CGS
Gumina <i>et al</i> [7] (1999)	45%	31.74%	12.50%
Verma U <i>et al</i> [11] (2017)	44%	38%	18%
Das SR <i>et al</i> [8] (2020)	55.78%	31.74%	12.50%
Present study	63%	25%	12%

Conclusion

The morphometric analysis of the coracoid process will help the radiologist and orthopedic surgeons for diagnosing various pathologies and plan for surgical procedure on coracoid process. It will help the orthopedic surgeons to operate the gleno-humeral joint during rotator cuff rupture, impingement syndrome, and for shoulder prosthesis in total shoulder arthroplasty.

They are also helpful in determination of gender by the forensic experts. Also useful in biomechanical engineering for designing implants for total shoulder replacement.

References

1. Standring S. Gray's Anatomy: The Anatomical basis of clinical practice. 41st edition. London: Elsevier ltd; 2016;801-4.
2. Bannister LH, Berry MM, Collins P, *et al*. Gray's Anatomy. 38th ed. Elsevier Churchill Livingstone; 2005:617-618.
3. Mohammed H, Skalski MR, Patel DB, Tomasian A, Schein AJ, White EA, *et al*. Coracoid process: the lighthouse of the shoulder. Radiographics. 2016; 29; 36(7):2084-101.
4. Rajan S, Ritika S, Kumar SR, Tripta S. Role of coracoid morphometry in subcoracoid impingement syndrome. The Internet J OrthopedicSurg. 2014;22(1):1-7.
5. Gallino M, Santamaria E, Doro T. Anthropometry of the scapula: clinical and surgical considerations. Journal of Shoulder and Elbow Surgery. 1998 May 1;7(3):284-91.
6. Matsen FA, Thomas SC, Rockwood CA. Anterior glenohumeral instability. In: The shoulder. Rockwood CA, Matsen FA, editors. Philadelphia. WB Saunders; 1990. p. 336-67
7. Gumina S, Postacchini F, Orsina L. The morphometry of the coracoid process- it's etiologic role in subcoracoid impingement syndrome. Int Orthop. 1999;23(4):198-201.
8. Das SR, Champatray S, Nayak G, Panda SK. Coracoid Process in Adult Human Scapula in Eastern Odisha Population: A Morphometric Analysis. Current Practice in Medical Science. 2022 Jul 25(7):12-22.
9. Piyawinijwong S, Sirisathira N, Chuncharunee A. The Scapula: osseous dimensions and gender dimorphism in Thais. Siriraj Med J. 2004; 56(7):356-365.
10. Coskun N, Karaali K, Cevikol C, Demirel BN, Sindel M. Anatomical basics and variations of the scapula in Turkish adults. Saudi Med J. 2006;27(9): 1320-5.
11. Verma U, Singroha R, Malik P, Rathee SK. A study on morphometry of coracoid process of scapula in north Indian

- population. Int J Res Med Sci 2017;5:4970-4.
12. Pahuja K, Singh J. Morphology of coracoid process and glenoid cavity in adult human scapulae. Int J Analytical Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Sci. 2014;2(2):19-22.
13. Khan R, Satyapal KS, Lazarus L, Naidoo N. An anthropometric evaluation of the scapula, with emphasis on the coracoid process and glenoid fossa in a South African population. Heliyon. 2020 Jan 1;6(1):e03107.